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ABSTRACT WORKSHOP ETHICAL REFLECTION FOR ENGINEERING CONFERENCE

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Reflection on societal and ethical aspects of technology is not yet commonly included in higher education programs. Most teachers are not sufficiently trained in ethical reflection and find it rather difficult to discuss ethical questions involving their own discipline with their students. However, nowadays ethical reflection on the impact and meaning of technological choices, makes up a necessary component of the research, design and development process. As future professionals (researchers included) our present students are expected to link options for technological innovations to the additional societal and ethical effects. Therefore, in this workshop the pertinent question about how ethical reflection can be made valuable and suitable for engineering programs, will be addressed

Ethical reflection on the impact of technology can take different forms, such as academic, societal -ethical and personal-ethical reflection. Academic reflection puts emphasizes on knowledge, theoretical frameworks and foundations (such as philosophy of technology); societal-ethical reflection deals with ethical questions in professional practices (for example about social implications of technical innovations in the own disciplines and about the consequences for society) whereas personal-ethical reflection stresses on one's own position towards one's profession (e.g. professional responsibility and professional identity).

At present, professional education programs tend to include personal-ethical reflection emphasizing on professional identity development (Trede, Macklin & Bridges, 2012) and on reflection on personal development from student to reflective practitioner during their studies (Mittendorff, 2014; Kember at all, 2008). Academic and societal- ethical reflection however, do not yet appear to be elementary parts of the curricula of (applied) engineering and science programs.

This lack is quite remarkable given the current request for ethical models from outside the educational context. Instruments and methods providing engineers and other professionals with most required tools for ethical reflection have been developed for professional practices, organizations and platforms. As such in The Netherlands, ECP (Platform voor de InformatieSamenleving) and philosopher Peter-Paul Verbeek recently published a joint edition of 'Ethical Accompaniment Approach' in which they explain a specific method to apply the thought of ethical accompaniment in everyday practice (Tijink & Verbeek, 2019). Steven Dorrestijn developed the Product Impact Tool, a model covering a repertoire of effects of technology ordered according to four different modes of interaction. Each mode is set

up with an interdisciplinary collection of relevant examples and useful concepts (see www.productimpacttool.org). By applying the tool in assessments and workshops for research projects about new technology, it evokes discussion and reflection about the impact of the (to be) designed product as well as about ethical concerns (Dorrestijn, 2017, in press). Finally, for a Space53 research project on new applications for drones Egbert Siebrand & Steven Dorrestijn designed an Ethical Readiness Tool. This tool can be complementary to a technical readiness level check and will be used to learn which ethical objections could obstruct social acceptance of a new technology (<https://www.space53.eu/evenementen/35/workshop-drone-acceptatie/>)

As the importance of the impact and ethics of technology in everyday practice of professional disciplines will only increase, we facilitate a dialogue in mixed groups of participants. This dialogue will be focused on three key questions:

1. Which reflective competences (attitude, skills and knowledge) on the impact of technology do our students need to develop being a critical professional and/or researcher in a way that is “practical” and fitting for academic and higher vocational education at engineering and science departments?
2. What (kind of) ethical reflection education is already being done? And, what should additionally be offered to engineering and science students at (applied) universities.
3. Which tools will be of good use and/or should be developed?

In the first part of the proposed workshop (30 min) the participants will exchange their thoughts and experiences in small groups. Starting point for these questions will be to bring up what parts ethical reflection are already been taken care of. And, to evaluate this current offered ethical reflection education. (question 2). Aim is to end with a generic outcome about vision and aim of reflective competences on the impact and ethics of technology (question 1).

In the second part (30 min) the participants will examine some recently developed methods and instruments and evaluate their experiences with them (question 3). Which approaches are qualified for ethical reflection in higher education? Which learning elements are important? And, what additional tools are specifically needed for proper reflection on the ethics and impact of technology in their own particular educational practices?

After the workshop (60 min) the participants will leave with ideas and tools about ethical reflection on the impact and ethics of technology in higher education

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